

THE GOAL OF IMPLEMENTING GENDER EQUALITY IS TO ACHIEVE SIGNIFICANT RESULTS

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Abstract: this article discusses the problems of gender equality in our country and their solutions. At the same time, the development and progress of management in the relations between men and women in the management of society and state affairs, as well as the tasks, relevance and importance of the gender equality strategy were analyzed and the need for further expansion of gender equality was revealed.

Key words: oppression, violence, openness, gender equality, strategy, politics, economy, women, men, society, law.

In recent years, achieving equal rights and opportunities for women and men, ensuring their equal participation in the management of society and state affairs, supporting women from a socio-legal point of view, as well as preventing women from oppression and violence Wide-scale reforms aimed at protection from violence are being implemented.

Legality, democracy, openness and transparency are the main principles of ensuring gender equality.

Within the framework of the gender strategy, the concept of gender equality means the equality of rights and opportunities of women and men in all spheres of life and activity, including politics, law, culture, education, science, and sports.

The main goal of the gender strategy is to ensure real equality of women and men, regardless of race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, faith, personal and social status.

What is gender equality?

What is gender equality? equality between men and women is one of the basic human rights. Also, gender equality is the basis of economic and social development. The concept of "gender" was introduced into our national legislation by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" dated September 3, 2019, according to which gender means women and girls. It is a social aspect of the relationship between men that is manifested in all spheres of society's life and activity, including politics, economy, law, ideology and culture, education and science.

Also, with this law, gender statistics - state statistics containing information on the status of women and men in all spheres of public life and activity, separately for each gender, of individuals of different genders. the part that reflects the relevant situation in all spheres of socio-political life, sheds light on gender issues and relations in society, gender-legal expertise - normative legal documents and their drafts guaranteeing equal rights and opportunities for women and men Concepts such as analysis of compliance with the principles of provision have also been included in our legislation.

Article 1 of this law states that the purpose of this law is to regulate relations in the field of ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men. powers in the field of

provision, guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men in the field of public service, equal participation of women and men in competitions for holding positions in the public service, election guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men in the exercise of their rights, guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men in the economic and social spheres, guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men in labor relations, family relations and child upbringing. Guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men, guarantees of equal relations in the performance of housework are established in the field.

Also, in this law, if a person believes that he has been directly or indirectly discriminated on the basis of gender, he has the right to appeal to the competent authorities or the court, in which the state duty is not charged to the person who has been directly or indirectly discriminated on the basis of gender, women and payment of fees for legal services provided by lawyers during the consideration of cases of violation of the equal rights of men in courts in accordance with the procedure established by law, their it is also provided that it will be reimbursed at the expense of the state.

The main tasks of the gender strategy are:

expansion of women's ownership of land and property;

To support the equal participation of women and men in all spheres of society's life and activities, including politics, economy, law, culture, education, science and sports, and to provide equal opportunities for them to take the lead in decision-making. create;

increase the political activity of women, change the negative views related to their place in society;

guaranteeing equal rights and opportunities for women and men in the field of employment, as well as creating decent jobs, developing women's entrepreneurship, expanding women's opportunities to receive loans from commercial banks;

to encourage women and men to study throughout their lives, to increase their medical culture in family planning and to strengthen their reproductive health, to promote a healthy lifestyle among them;

creation of effective organizational and legal mechanisms for combating human trafficking and forced labor, preventing oppression and violence, identifying and eliminating them;

strengthening the family, increasing the responsibility of all family members in family relations, preventing early marriage, marriage between close relatives, early childbirth and family separation;

budget planning in promoting the principles of gender equality, equal realization of the rights and opportunities of women and men, integration of gender issues into budget processes, improvement of gender statistics management;

implementation of comprehensive measures to improve Uzbekistan's position in international rankings and indexes assessing gender equality, women's entrepreneurship, oppression and violence against women and men;

increasing the role of parliament, civil society institutions and media in achieving the national goals of ensuring gender equality in the field of sustainable development and expanding the rights and opportunities of all women;

gender tenglik sohasidagi xalqaro shartnomalardan kelib chiqadigan majburiyatlarning bajarilishini ta'minlash, O'zbekiston Respublikasining milliy manfaatlariga mos bo'lgan xalqaro shartnomalarni ratifikatsiya qilish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlarni amalga oshirish.

Gender equality, that is, the equality of men and women, is one of the basic human rights. Recent studies show that this factor is the basis of the highest level of economic, social and political development. Because according to experts, work teams consisting of 50/50 men and women, especially if they are engaged in mental work, show several times higher results than a team consisting of only men. In addition, gender equality is an indicator of the country's level of democratic development. So, in order to join the ranks of developed countries and attract more and more investments to our country, we should attach sufficient importance to this indicator.

There are issues that require increasing the attention of women in the development of the state and society, socio-economic, education, healthcare and other socio-economic spheres. In particular, it is necessary to ensure the expansion of women's participation in decision-making on current issues of state and community management on an equal basis with men.

CONCLUSION. Significant results are expected from the implementation of gender equality. In particular, it expands the practice of appointing women to leadership positions of state bodies in the upper and lower system. By introducing a temporary quota system in state bodies with gender imbalance, balance between women and men is ensured. Providing employment to women in need of social protection and underprivileged families, especially in rural areas, increasing the effectiveness of work on creating decent working conditions and providing them with social support, as well as self-employment. The most important thing is to prevent cases of harassment and violence against women in the workplace, and to end the negative attitudes towards women in the society. Ensuring gender equality, first of all, serves to accelerate the socio-economic and political development of our country, which means to increase the well-being of the people, to solve many problems in society, and to change our daily life for the better.

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